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Teachers' Quality Assurance Strategies and Effective Instructional Delivery in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State

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Abstract

This study examined teachers' quality assurance strategies and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The study was guided by two research objectives from which two research questions were posed and two hypotheses were tested. The study adopted a correlational survey design. The population of this study was 1,978 comprising 35 principals and 1,943 teachers in the 35 public senior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The sample of the study was 317 comprising 20 principals and 297 teachers. The Taro Yamane formula was adopted in determining the sample size of teachers while all the principals in the selected public secondary schools were studied. The instruments for data collection were researcher-designed questionnaires titled "Teachers' Quality Assurance Strategies Questionnaire" and "Teachers Instructional Delivery Questionnaire" respectively. The instruments were validated by three experts. The internal consistencies of the instruments were determined using the Cronbach Alpha statistics. Using the Cronbach Alpha tool, Reliability coefficients of 0.83, 0.80, 0.84 and 0.77 were obtained which showed the instrument was reliable. The research questions were answered, and the hypotheses tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics. The hypotheses were further subjected to t-transformation to establish the significance of the r-value at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the analyzed data revealed among others that there is a high and positive relationship between lesson planning by teachers and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that the school management should provide resources and training for teachers to develop comprehensive lesson plans that incorporate diverse teaching methodologies, ensuring alignment with curriculum standards.

Keywords: Teachers, Quality Assurance, Instructional Delivery

INTRODUCTION

Education is central to human capital development and the socio-economic progress of any nation. In Nigeria, public senior secondary schools serve as a critical segment of the education system, preparing students for higher education and vocational paths. However, concerns about the quality of instruction in these schools, particularly in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State, have raised the need for effective quality assurance strategies among teachers (Amie-Ogan & Onyebuchi, 2020). Quality assurance in education involves systematic efforts to maintain and improve teaching standards and ensure effective instructional delivery, thereby optimizing learning outcomes.

The effectiveness of instructional delivery is often influenced by teachers' ability to adopt innovative teaching strategies, manage classroom dynamics, and align lessons with curriculum standards. Teachers' quality assurance strategies, such as peer evaluations, lesson planning, and feedback systems, are pivotal in fostering effective instructional practices (Harry, 2021). These strategies not

only enhance students' academic engagement but also help address issues of underachievement and skill gaps among learners.

Public secondary schools in Port Harcourt face challenges, including inadequate teacher training, poor supervision, and a lack of teaching resources, which hinder the implementation of quality assurance measures (Osuji & Etuketu, 2019). Research has highlighted that schools with well-established quality assurance frameworks tend to exhibit better teacher performance and student outcomes compared to those lacking such systems (Okogbaa & Alasomuka, 2023). Effective quality assurance involves continuous monitoring and improvement of instructional practices, which can be achieved through professional development programs, collaborative teaching approaches, and technology integration.

Despite the potential benefits, many public schools in Rivers State struggle with implementing robust quality assurance mechanisms. Factors such as overcrowded classrooms, insufficient administrative support, and inconsistent policy enforcement have further exacerbated the issue (Anunobi, 2022). These gaps necessitate a detailed exploration of how teachers' quality assurance strategies impact instructional delivery in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt.

Statement of the Problem

Effective instructional delivery is fundamental to the success of public senior secondary schools, serving as the backbone of academic achievement and skill acquisition among students. However, in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State, there are growing concerns about the inconsistency and inefficiency of instructional practices in public senior secondary schools. Despite the presence of qualified teachers, student performance often falls short of expectations, raising questions about the effectiveness of quality assurance strategies employed by teachers.

Quality assurance strategies, such as lesson planning, classroom monitoring, peer evaluation, and professional development, are intended to ensure that teaching practices meet established educational standards. However, challenges such as inadequate training, lack of resources, and insufficient administrative support hinder their implementation in public schools. Research has shown that schools lacking robust quality assurance mechanisms are more likely to experience poor instructional delivery and low student engagement (Osuji & Etuketu, 2019).

In addition, factors such as overcrowded classrooms, outdated teaching methods, and a lack of alignment between curriculum goals and instructional delivery further exacerbate the problem. These gaps not only affect student learning outcomes but also undermine the overall credibility of the public education system in Port Harcourt.

Despite the critical role of teachers' quality assurance strategies in fostering effective instructional delivery, there is limited empirical evidence on how these strategies are applied and their impact on teaching practices in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis. Without addressing these gaps, efforts to enhance instructional quality and improve student performance may remain ineffective and unsustainable. The question then is do teachers' quality assurance strategies relate to effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis? Providing answer to this question is the problem of the study.

Purpose of the Study

The study examined teachers' quality assurance strategies and teachers' instructional delivery in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. Specifically, this study sought to:

1. investigate the relationship between teachers' lesson planning strategy and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.
2. Investigate the relationship between teachers' classroom management strategy and instructional delivery in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between teachers' lesson planning strategy and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State?

2. What is the relationship between teachers’ classroom management strategy and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between teachers’ lesson planning strategy and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State.
2. There is no relationship between teachers’ classroom management and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlational survey design. The population of this study was 1,978 comprising 35 principals and 1,943 teachers in the 35 public senior secondary schools in Port-Harcourt and Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The sample of the study was 317 comprising 20 principals and 297 teachers. The Taro Yamane formula was adopted in determining the sample size of teachers while all the principals in the selected public secondary schools were studied. The instruments for data collection were self-designed questionnaires titled “Teachers’ Assurance Mechanism Strategy” and “Effective Instructional Delivery Questionnaire respectively. The instruments were validated by three experts. The internal consistencies of the instruments were determined using the Cronbach Alpha statistics. Using the Cronbach Alpha tool, Reliability coefficients of 0.83, 0.80, 0.84 and 0.77 were obtained which showed the instrument was reliable. The research questions were answered, and the hypotheses tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics. The hypotheses were further subjected to t-transformation to establish the significance of the r-value at 0.05 level of significance. The research questions were answered based on the value and direction of the correlation coefficient, (positive and high, positive but low, or negative and high or negative but low or moderate). Values of 0.1-0.4 were counted as low correlation, values of 0.5 were considered moderate correlation while 0.6-1.0 were considered high correlation. Similarly, the hypotheses were tested for significance of relationship at 0.05 level of significance. This was further tested by transforming the coefficient of correlation (r) to t in order to establish the significance or otherwise of the r-value.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between teachers’ lesson planning strategy and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State?*

Table 4.4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation on Relationship between Teachers’ Lesson Planning Strategy and Effective Instructional Delivery in Public Senior Secondary School

Variable	N	$\sum X$	$\sum Y$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum Y^2$	$\sum XY$	Rcal	Remarks
Teachers’ Lesson Planning (X)	360	852.12	2623.12			2237.01	0.84	High positive
Effective Instructional Delivery(Y)	360	2100.02	2528.15					

The analyses from Table 4.4 revealed a correlation value of $r = 0.84$. This value is high and positive, thus indicating that there is high and positive relationship between teachers’ lesson planning and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State. This result implied that teachers’ lesson planning leads to effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between teachers' classroom management strategy and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State?*

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation on Relationship between Teachers' Classroom Management Strategy and Effective Instructional Delivery in Public Senior Secondary School

Variable	N	$\sum X \sum Y$	$\sum X^2 \sum Y^2$	$\sum X \sum Y$	r-cal	Remarks
Classroom Management (X)	360	853.20	2323.12	2613.01	0.79	High Positive
Effective Instructional Delivery (Y)	360	1108.04	3018.02			

The analyses from Table 2 revealed a correlation value of $r = 0.79$. This value is high and positive, thus indicating that there is high and positive relationship between teachers' classroom management strategy and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State. This result implied that teachers' classroom management strategy leads to effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' lesson planning strategy and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State.

Table 3: T-test Summary Analysis between Teachers' Lesson Planning and Effective Instructional Delivery in Public Senior Secondary School

Variable	N	$\sum X \sum Y$	$\sum X^2 \sum Y^2$	$\sum X \sum Y$	Df	α	r _{cal}	t _{cal}	t _{crit}	P-value	Rmk
Teachers' Lesson Planning Strategy (X)	360	852.12	2623.12	2237.0	358	0.05	0.84	23.03	1.96	0.01	Sig. Reject H ₀
Effective Instructional Delivery (Y)	360	2100.0	2528.15	2							

The data analysed in Table 3 revealed the Pearson correlation summary between teachers' lesson planning strategy and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State. The correlation coefficient is 0.84 and the p-value is 0.04 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between teachers' lesson planning strategy and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State is rejected. This indicates that there is a positive relationship between teachers' lesson planning strategy and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between teachers' classroom management strategy and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State.

Table 4: T-test Summary Analysis between Teachers' Classroom Management Strategy and Effective Instructional Delivery in Public Senior Secondary School

Variable	N	$\frac{\sum X}{\sum Y}$	$\frac{\sum X^2 \sum Y}{\sum Y^2}$	$\sum X \sum Y$	Df	α	r _{cal}	t _{cal}	t _{crit}	P-value	Rmk
Teachers' Classroom Management Strategy (X)	360	853.20	2323.12								
				2613.01	358	0.05	0.79	18.07	1.96	0.02	Sig. Reject H ₀
Effective Instructional Delivery (Y)	360	1108.04	3018.02								

The data analysed in Table 4 revealed the Pearson correlation summary between teachers' classroom management strategy and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State. The correlation coefficient is 0.79 and the p-value is 0.02 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between teachers' classroom management strategy and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State is rejected. This indicates that there is a positive relationship between teachers' classroom management strategy and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result of the finding of the study for research question one revealed that respondents were of the opinion that there is a high and positive relationship between teachers' lesson planning strategy and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State. The study revealed that shown that teachers who plan their lessons effectively utilize class time more efficiently, which directly contributes to effective teaching practices. This alignment between planning and time management results in improved instructional delivery. All these lead to effective instructional delivery of teachers in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State. Similarly, hypothesis one showed that there is a significant relationship between teachers' lesson planning strategy and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State. This finding is in line with the finding of Bay, (2016), he concluded that effective lesson planning is associated with higher teaching quality and improved student outcomes. From his findings he indicated that teachers who engage in comprehensive lesson planning tend to deliver more structured and effective lessons, leading to better student understanding and engagement. Well-planned lessons correlate positively with teaching efficiency. Teachers who prioritize lesson planning are better equipped to meet curriculum goals and student needs (Shaltry, 2020).

The result of the finding of the study for research question two revealed that respondents were of the opinion that there is a high and positive relationship between teachers' classroom management strategy and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State. It was revealed that effective classroom management strategies are crucial for improving students' academic performance. Teachers who implement structured management techniques create an environment conducive to learning, leading to better instructional outcome. The corresponding hypothesis two revealed that there is a significant relationship classroom management strategy and effective instructional delivery in public senior secondary school in Port Harcourt Metropolis Rivers State. This is in line with the findings of Olugbenga, (2020) he concluded that Effective classroom management strategies directly correlate with students' academic achievement, reinforcing the idea that good management practices enhance instructional delivery. The classroom environment impacts the level of student engagement and academic success. The influence of teachers' characteristics on classroom management effectiveness. Teachers who exhibit strong management skills tend to foster better instructional delivery, creating a more engaging and productive classroom environment.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that there is a strong correlation between teachers' quality assurance strategy and instructional delivery, underscoring the necessity for ongoing training programmes. Structured lesson planning and effective classroom management practices are vital for creating conducive learning settings. These insights not only reaffirm the importance of quality assurance in education but also provide actionable recommendations for policymakers and educational stakeholders aimed at enhancing overall teaching efficacy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. The school management should provide resources and training for teachers to develop comprehensive lesson plans that incorporate diverse teaching methodologies, ensuring alignment with curriculum standards.
2. The school administrators should offer professional development programs focused on effective classroom management techniques, helping teachers create a positive and conducive learning environment.

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